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individual" [1; 62]. Many students spend more and more time studying not only English, but also at least one or two foreign languages. You can find a combination of English, Spanish, German and Chinese. Also, knowledge of a foreign language can help to get an education abroad. Such education can be either additional to the existing, or basic, directly related to future professional activities.

Students with knowledge of the language have the opportunity of training programs that will help to acquire not only invaluable experience, but also give the opportunity to get acquainted with the structure of foreign business, learn about the latest developments and trends in the development of the sphere of interest, improve the language and expand knowledge about the culture of the country. Employers are interested in having as their employees specialists who speak the language, regardless of the intensity of its use. The exception - rare professionals with extensive experience, but here the ideal will still be a candidate who knows the language. The degree of language proficiency is an indicator of the level of education of a person and his prospects for the company. And the higher the position, the more serious the language requirements. Top management speaks English "by default", because it is an element of prestige and image. English is the working language of Pro-Western companies, it is used for all internal documentation, correspondence and meetings. In international

companies, knowledge of a foreign language is a mandatory requirement for all professionals.

Knowledge of English is one of the conditions of employment in companies operating in foreign markets or having foreign partners (and such in Russia is becoming more and more). Moreover, such a requirement is put not only before candidates for "top" positions, but also before middle-level employees. In 30 % of vacancy announcements, employers require the candidate to speak basic, spoken or fluent English - depending on the position. Verification of this knowledge, as a rule, occurs already at the stage of consideration of the summary and the first interview. As for Russian organizations, many of them cooperate with foreign partners and also want their employees to know English. But it is worth noting that a limited number of Russian companies have positions that require a combination of professional education and active use of a foreign language. Learning a language can be successful only when it is relevant to the business in which the person is engaged. Analyzing various professional situations, the language learner learns a whole set of words and expressions, which are combined into a group, so that each subsequent new expression is a natural consequence of the previous one. This allows a person to focus more deeply and fully on those aspects of the English language that reflect the specifics of his professional activity, so the learning process can be relatively simple, easy and specific.

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ЭРНЕСТ ХЕМИНГУЭЙНИНГ “ЧОЛ ВА ДЕНГИЗ” АСАРИДАГИ ИБОРАЛИ ФЕЪЛЛАРНИНГ ТАРЖИМАСИ БОРАСИДА

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Annotation: this article discusses the peculiar sides of Uzbek translation of phrasal verbs in the work “The old Man and the Sea” by Ernest Hemingway, done by Ibrohim Gafurov. The translation issues of phrasal verbs in English is analysed in comparison with Uzbek variations.

Keywords: phrasal verbs, translation, “The old Man and the Sea”.

Ҳар қандай тилларнинг ўзига хос хусусиятларини очиб беришда иборали феъллар муҳим рол ўйнайди. Жумладан, инглиз тилида ҳам бу ўз аксини топади. Шу сабабли, инглиз тилини ўрганувчилар учун иборали феълларни тадқиқ қилиш долзарб саналади.

Инглиз тилини хорижий тил сифатида ўрганувчилар иборали феълларни нафақат нутқда қўллашда, балки таржима қилишда ҳам баъзи муаммоларга дуч келади. Бу эса улардан иборали феълларнинг таржима қилинишида унинг ўзига хос хусусиятларини ёки фарқлинишларини чуқур ўрганишини талаб этади. Шуни таъкидлаб ўтиш

лозимки, ўзбек тилида айнан инглиз тилидагидек иборали феъл тушунчаси мавжуд эмас ва улар ўзбек тилида оддий феълларга тенгдир. Шунинг учун инглиз тилидаги иборали феълларни ўрганиш ва таржима қилишда бу бирликларга оид умумий тушунчага эга бўлиш мақсадга мувофиқдир.

Иборали феъллар – бу, мустақил феъллар ва улар билан бирикма ҳосил қилувчи предлог ёки равишлар иштирокида ўзига хос маъно ҳосил қилувчи иборавий бирикмалардир.[3, 6] Лекин бу барқарорлик таржимада ҳар доим ҳам ўз аксини топмайди. Шунга кўра бу бирикмалар бошқа тилларга оддий феъл, қўшма феъл ёки ибора тарзида ёхуд матн

мазмунига ҳамоҳанг тарзда табдил қилиниши мумкин. Бу ўз ўрнида иборали феъллар билан боғлиқ муаммолар ҳали етарлича эканлигини англатади. Фикримизнинг далили сифатида, Эрнест Хемингуэйнинг “Чол ва денгиз” қиссасидан олинган намуналар мисолида таҳлил қилсак. Масалан:

“When the wind was in the east a smell came across the harbour from the shark factory; but today there was only the faint edge of the odour because the wind had backed into the north and then dropped off and it was pleasant and sunny on the Terrace.” [1, 2]

Келинг, ушбу парчани тўғридан тўғри таржима қилиб кўрайлик:

“Шамол шарқдалигида қанақадир ҳид ақула фабрикасидан кўрфазни кесиб ўтиб келарди. Аммо бугун фақатгина билинар-билинмас ҳид бор еди холос чунки шамол шимолга қараб йўналган ва кейин тўхтаган еди. Террасда ҳаво ажойиб ва қўйи эди.”

Албатта, бир қарашда белгиланган иборали феъллар (come across, back into, drop off) бизга маълум бўлган маънолари билан ифодаланиб осонгина таржима қилса бўладигандек кўринади. Лекин асл таржимада улар қуйидагича акс этган:

“Шамол шарқдан эсди дегунча, ўзи билан ақула корхонасининг қўланса ҳидини олиб келарди; аммо бугун ҳид деярли сезилмас, чунки шамол шимолдан эса бошлаб, кўп ўтмай бутунлай тинган эди. Шунинг учун ҳам Террас серкўйи ва сўлим эди.” [2, 2]

Иборали феълларни таржима қилиш жараёнида шу бирикмалар қўлланилаётган вазият ва нутқий ҳолат қанчалик муҳим бўлса, уларнинг структураси ҳам шунчалик аҳамиятлидир. Сабаби, иборали феъллар турли тузилишларга эга бўлганлиги учун уларнинг маънолари ҳам ҳар хил тушунчаларни англатади. Мисол учун, юқоридаги намунада келтирилган drop off иборали феъли ўтимли феъл сифатида келса, *“тушириб юбормоқ”, “ташлаб кетмоқ”* ёки *“олиб қайтмоқ”* маъноларини англатади:

He dropped off the glass (У стаканни тушириб юборди)

I dropped my sister off from school. (Мен синглимни мактабдан олиб қайтдим)

Агар ўтимсиз феъл сифатида келса уйкуга кетмоқ ёки бояги вазиятдан келиб чиқиб тинмоқ, тўхтамоқ маъноларини англатади:

“...the wind backed into the north and then dropped off ...”

“...шамол шимолдан эса бошлаб, кўп ўтмай тинган эди.”

Эрнест Хемингуэйнинг инглиз тилида ёзилган “Чол ва денгиз” қиссасида учрайдиган иборали феълларнинг таржимаси фразеологик луғатларда келтирилган таржималарига мос тушмайди. Бу эса таржимондан контекстни чуқур ўрганиб, нутқий фаолиятга асос бўлаётган факторларни инobatта олишни талаб қилади, яъни иборали феъллар қўлланилаётган нутқий вазият, суҳбатдошларнинг бир-бирига бўлган муносабати ва шу каби катор жиҳатларга эътибор қаратиш лозимлигини англатади.

Масалан, қуйидаги мисолни кўриб чиқайлик: *“The shivering increased as he pulled in and he could see the blue back of the fish in the water and the gold of his sides before he swung him over the side and into the boat. He lay in the stern in the sun, compact and bullet shaped, his big, unintelligent eyes staring as he thumped his life out against the planking of the boat with the quick shivering strokes of his neat, fast-moving tail.” [1, 10]* Бу намуна таржимон томонидан қуйидагича таржима қилинган:

“У ўлжани қайиққа чиқариб олиб, бордан ошириб ташламасиданоқ, балиқнинг зангори сирти ва олтинсимон жилва қилган биқинларини кўрди. Миқтидан келган, худди қуйиб қўйилган ўқдек тунец қайиқнинг кунгай саҳнида ётар ва маънисиз катта кўзларини ола-қула қилиб, сип-силлиқ, серҳаракат қуйругини жонҳолатда биланглата-биланглата ҳаёт билан видолашарди.” [2, 11-12]

Ушбу асар таржимасидаги яна бир эътиборли ҳолатни кўриб ўтсак:

“The successful fishermen of that day were already in and had butchered their marlin out and carried them laid full length across two planks, with two men staggering at the end of each plank, to the fish house where they waited for the ice truck to carry them to the market in Havana.” [1, 1-2]

Бу намуна таржимон Иброҳим Ғофуров таржимасида қуйидагича берилган: *“Бугун иши ўнгидан келганлар овдан аллақачон қайтишган ва ўлжа марлинларини тозалаб, бир жуфт тахта устига кўндаланг қўйишганча тўртовлашиб уларни балиқ омборига этиб топширишган эди.” [2, 2]*

Ушбу парчада келтирилган waited for иборали феъли тушириб қолдирилган. Негаки, бу таржимада унга эҳтиёж йўқ.

Юқоридагидек иборали феълларнинг тушириб қолдирилиш ҳолатларини кўп учратишимиз мумкин. Бундай вазиятларда ўша бирикмаларнинг таржима мазмунида қанчалик аҳамиятли эканлигини ҳисобга олиш зарур. Шунақа вазиятга ўхшаш қуйидаги парчани ҳам кўриб чиксак:

“He let the line slip through his fingers while he reached down with his left hand and made fast the free end of the two reserve coils to the loop of the two reserve coils of the next line.” [1, 11]

Таржимоннинг бу ҳолатга баҳоси қуйидагича:

“У чилвирни ўз ҳолига қўйиб берди-да, чап қўли билан икки эҳтиёт калаванинг бўйи учини, бошқа қармоқнинг икки эҳтиёт калавасига улади.” [2, 13-14].

Гувоҳи бўлганингиздек, ушбу вазиятда ҳам slip through феъли таржимада ўз ҳолига қўйиб берди дея ўғирилган. Ушбу қиссани иборали феълларга боғлаган ҳолда қиёсан ўрганиш натижасида шундай ҳулосага келиш мумкинки, иборали феълларнинг таржима хусусиятлари чексиздир. Ёш таржимонларда кўпроқ адабиётлар билан ишлаш натижасида амалий кўникмаларни шакллантира бориб, бу каби муаммоларни ҳал қила олиш ва бундан таржима жараёнларида унумли фойдаланишга эришишлари мумкин.

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АННОТАЦИЯ:

В данной статье рассматриваются специфические стороны узбекского перевода фразовых глаголов в работе Эрнеста Хемингуэя «Старик и море», выполненной Иброхимом Гафуровым. Проблемы перевода фразовых глаголов в английском языке анализируются в сравнении с узбекскими вариациями.

Ключевые слова: фразовые глаголы, перевод «Старик и море»

THE CONTENT OF TEACHING GRAMMAR

**Shadmanov Sherzod Khursanaliyevich, teacher
Kokand State Pedagogical Institute**

Abstract: Content of teaching materials of language claimed as part of teaching grammar. Content of teaching grammar envelopes a teaching part of grammar phenomena with the help of special rules and particular exercises.

Keywords: teaching grammar, method, approach, complex phenomenon, speech, based on.

Nowadays, the demand on learning foreign languages is increasing day by day. In addition, the methodology of teaching languages is also developing. Conditions of reforming of all education system the question of the world assistance to improvement of quality of scientific-theoretical aspect of educational process is especially actually put. As President I.A.Karimov has declared in the program speech "Harmoniously development of generation a basis of progress of Uzbekistan"; "... all of us realize, that achievement of the great purposes put today before us, noble aspirations it is necessary for updating a society, today when we celebrating the 28th anniversary of the National Independence of our Motherland". The effect and destiny of our reforms carried out in the name of progress and the future, results of our intentions are connected with highly skilled, conscious staff the experts who are meeting the requirements of time.

Grammar is defined by Ur (1991: 4) as "the way language manipulates and combines words (or bits of words) in order to form longer units of meaning." This definition is quite close to the common understanding of what grammar is. The main difference is that it tells us how the rules of language actually work – they arrange and shape words. Nevertheless, knowing what these rules do is not a very motivating factor alone.

Crystal (2004) says, "Grammar is the structural foundation of our ability to express ourselves. The more we are aware of how it works, the more we can monitor the meaning and effectiveness of the way we and others use language. It can help foster precision, detect ambiguity, and exploit the richness of expression available in English. Additionally, it can help everyone, not only teachers of English, but teachers of anything for all teaching grammar is ultimately a matter of getting to grips with meaning."

Maugham (1938) adds, "It is necessary to know grammar, and it is better to write grammatically than not, but it is well to remember that grammar is common speech formulated. Usage is the only test."

As it can be seen from the above definitions, grammar is not an unimportant set of rules that can be ignored without consequences. It is a very complex phenomenon and even though learners may find it a difficult thing to master, the time devoted to that is certainly not wasted. Making students realize it, however, is only the first step in teaching grammar, and the following activities can take many different forms, based on a selected approach and method.

Content of teaching materials of language claimed as part of teaching grammar. Content of teaching grammar envelopes a teaching part of grammar phenomena with the help of special rules (not exact rules but models or algorithms) and particular exercises. We can say that each side of grammar phenomenon, two or three of them (function, semantics, and form) can be placed in content of teaching grammar.

Units of the English languages can be divided into the two following groups according to their difficulty: 1) the most complicated grammar phenomena in which quantity of mistakes increases while changing grades; 2) average difficult grammar -occurrences which quantity of mistakes are met in different grades; 3) grammar occurrences in which reducing quantity of mistakes are considered or no mistakes during occurring speech.

It is clear from schooling experiences that some occurrences are taught easily. For example, the usage of the nouns in plural, function of possessive, meaning of prepositions, etc.

There exist other grammar occurrences in which mistakes are quickly resolved with the help of a teacher's footnote (ordinary general rule). But

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